

SMART FISHWAYS

W2 – Installation of the WLN in field fishways

D2.1 Field study cases and installation

Abstract

The 'Field Study Cases and Installation' deliverable offers a detailed description of the various study cases examined during the Smart Fishways project, with special emphasis on those installations considered permanent within the project. Additional information on the architecture of the installed networks is also provided.

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The **Smart Fishways** project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101032024.

Contents

Project information	2
Document Control Page	3
1. Introduction.....	4
2. Fishways	4
2.1. Guma	4
2.2. Vadocondes	5
2.3. Quintana	6
2.4. Poncebos	7
2.5. La Nazas	8
2.6. Bera	9
3. Gauging Stations.....	10
3.1. Agauntza	10
3.2. Leitzaran	10
4. Hydropeaking (Portugal)	11
4.1. Covas do Barroso	11
4.2. Bragado	11

Project information

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<i>Project number</i>	101032024
<i>Project acronym</i>	Smart Fishways
<i>Project title</i>	Adapting fishways to hydrological and climatic uncertainty
<i>Starting date</i>	01/09/2021
<i>Duration</i>	2 years
<i>Call identifier</i>	MSCA-IF-2020 - Individual Fellowships
<i>Abstract</i>	<p>Modern society currently requires large volumes of fresh water. The result is the installation of river barriers, causing the fragmentation of habitats as well as changes in the ecology of freshwater systems. Stepped fishways can allow fish to move freely up rivers to complete their life cycle. However, the variability of rivers modifies the hydraulic conditions within fishways, affecting the free movement of fish.</p> <p>Smart Fishways is an EU-funded project, which aims to assess the effect of hydrological variability on stepped fishways and to develop a technological and methodological framework to monitor fishways' performance in real-time. By combining fish biology, hydraulics and sensor networks, a new generation of smart fishways will be created, capable of self-deciding their optimal configuration.</p>
<i>Work Package number</i>	W2 Installation of the WLN in field fishways
<i>Deliverable</i>	D2.1 Field study cases and installation

Document Control Page

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<i>Title</i>	D2.1 Field study cases and installation
<i>Creator</i>	Juan Francisco Fuentes-Pérez
<i>Description</i>	The 'Field Study Cases and Installation' deliverable offers a detailed description of the various study cases examined during the Smart Fishways project, with special emphasis on those installations considered permanent within the project. Additional information on the architecture of the installed networks is also provided
<i>Publisher</i>	Smart Fishways
<i>Contributors</i>	Juan Francisco Fuentes-Pérez (IP), Francisco Javier Sanz Ronda (Supervisor)
<i>Creation date</i>	29/02/2022
<i>Type</i>	Text
<i>Language</i>	en-GB
<i>Rights</i>	Copyright "Smart Fishways and University of Valladolid"
<i>Audience</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/> Classified
<i>Status</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> In Progress <input type="checkbox"/> For Review <input type="checkbox"/> For Approval <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Approved

History of changes			
<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Modified by</i>	<i>Comments</i>
1	10/12/2021	Juan Francisco Fuente-Pérez	Version 1
1	28/07/2022	Juan Francisco Fuente-Pérez	Revision
1	26/12/2023	Juan Francisco Fuente-Pérez	Revision
1	18/01/2024	Juan Francisco Fuente-Pérez	Revision

1. Introduction

Work Package 2 was dedicated to the installation of the Smart Fishways network in various field study cases. Although scheduled from M01 to M21 of the project, the work was primarily executed during the initial days of the installation periods. We surpassed the initial plan by deploying a network across multiple study cases in Spain and Portugal, including two continuous installations and eight others installed during different migration periods of target species. By seizing the opportunity to apply our technology to a broader range of fish passage challenges beyond traditional fishways, we extended our research to assess passage through gauging structures and evaluate the impact of hydropeaking. (Table 1).

Table 1. List of study cases covered in Smart Fishways. In blue the ongoing ones.

Study case	Location	Date	Target species	Description
Guma	Burgos, Spain	28/02/2022 (ongoing)	Iberian barbel and nase	Submerged notch and orifice fishway
Vadocondes	Burgos, Spain	01/04/2022 (ongoing)	Iberian barbel and nase	Vertical Slot fishway
Quintana	Palencia, Spain	04/07/2022 - 22/09/2022	Iberian barbel	Mixed fishway
Poncebos	Asturias, Spain	11/10/2022 - 03/02/2023	Brown trout	Pool-weir fishway (plunging performance)
Bragado	Vila Pouca de Aguar, Portugal	27/07/2022 (ongoing)	Small Cyprinids	Hydropeaking
Covas do Barroso	Boticas, Portugal	26/07/2022 - 09/10/2023	Small Cyprinids	Hydropeaking
Leitzaran	Gipuzkoa, Spain	06/10/2023 - 20/12/2023	Brown trout	V-Flat gauging station
Agauntza	Gipuzkoa, Spain	06/10/2023 - 20/12/2023	Brown trout	V-Flat gauging station
Las Nazas	Navarra, Spain	04/10/2023 - 20/12/2023	Brown trout	Submerged notch and orifice fishway
Bera	Navarra, Spain	04/10/2023 - 20/12/2023	Brown trout	Pool-weir fishway (plunging performance)

2. Fishways

2.1. Guma

It is a fishway located in the Duero River, near Guma village in the northwest part of Spain (41°38'13.9"N 3°32'36.9"W) (Figure 1). The fishway is composed by 36 cross-walls with submerged notches and bottom orifices (notch width (b_n) = 0.3 m; sill height (p) = 0.8 m; orifice size = 0.175 m (width- b_o) x 0.175 m (height- a_o) and 35 pools (length = 2.6 m; width = 1.6 m; slope = 8.6 %), with mean water drops (ΔH) of 0.25 m, mean water depth in the pools (h_o) of 1.2 m and volumetric power dissipation of 121±10 W/m³.

Figure 1. Installation of the sensor network at Guma fishway.

The sensor network consists of 15 sensors (Figure A1):

- 12 nodes with ultrasound sensors.
- 1 node with ultrasound, water temperature, barometric pressure, air temperature, humidity, and luminosity.
- 2 nodes with ultrasound and water temperature.

In addition, together with the sensors to collect biological information a PIT-Tag system with 4 antennas has been installed, which would be substituted by a custom-developed fish counter in the next monitoring campaign (2023-2024).

All the data is collected, processed, and transmitted (Lora radio + mobile connectivity) by a single Gateway that consists of a Raspberry Pi computer.

Additionally, during the 2023 campaign, a PIT-Tag tracker was developed and installed. This device, a dummy PIT-Tag, can be programmed for periodic activation, allowing for the automatic assessment of the PIT-Tag System's performance.

2.2. Vadocondes

It is a fishway located in the mainstem of the Duero River, in Vadocondes village (Burgos) in the northwest part of Spain ($41^{\circ}38'16''$ N, $3^{\circ}34'17''$ W) (Figure A2.a and A2.b). It is a vertical slot fishway composed of 26 cross-walls (slot width (b_s) = 0.2 m) and 25 pools (length = 2.1 m; width = 1.6 m; slope = 6.5%) with mean water drops (ΔH) of 0.15 m, mean water depth in the pools (h_0) of 0.92 m, and mean volumetric power dissipation of 122 ± 7 W/m³.

Figure 2. Installation of the sensor network at Vadocondes.

The sensor network consists of 10 sensors (Figure 2):

- 12 nodes with ultrasound sensors.
- 1 node with ultrasound, water temperature, barometric pressure, air temperature, humidity, and luminosity.
- 2 nodes with ultrasound and water temperature.

In addition, together with the sensors to collect biological information a PIT-Tag system with 3 antennas has been installed, which would be substituted by a custom-developed fish counter in the next monitoring campaign (2023-2024).

All the data is collected, processed, and transmitted (Lora radio + mobile connectivity) by a single Gateway that consists of a Raspberry Pi computer.

Additionally, during the 2023 campaign, a PIT-Tag tracker was developed and installed. This device, a dummy PIT-Tag, can be programmed for periodic activation, allowing for the automatic assessment of the PIT-Tag System's performance.

2.3. Quintana

This study site consists of a mixed fishway; the downstream section is a vertical slot fishway, and the upstream section is a submerged notch and orifice fishway. It is located at the Quintana del Puente hydropower plant on the Arlanza River (42° 4' 25.92" N, 4° 13' 7.56" W; Palencia, North-Central Spain). In this study case, two setups were established. The first one was aimed at conducting specific experiments on hydrological variability, with sensors positioned in the vertical slot fishway section. This section of the fishway comprises nine pools (2.10 m long and 1.60 m wide), separated by eight vertical slots (0.20 m-wide slots), and features a bottom slope of 6.5%. The theoretical water drop between pools is 0.15 m, the mean water depth in design conditions is 0.92 m, and the VPD in the pools is approximately 130 W/m³. There is a gate in the upstream slot to control the flow discharge through the fishway. During this network configuration, water levels were continuously monitored (every 5 min, with 0.5 cm precision) using a network of 5 ultrasound sensors, 1 node with ultrasound, water temperature, barometric pressure, air temperature, humidity, and luminosity sensors, and a PIT-Tag system with 4 antennas. All the data was collected, processed, and transmitted (Lora radio + mobile connectivity) by a single Gateway that consists of a Raspberry Pi computer (Figure 3a).

After this initial experiment, which lasted 2 days, the setup was reconfigured using the same number of nodes to study the performance of the entire fishway (Figure 3b). Specifically, this included the nine

cross-walls consisting of vertical slots described earlier and seven cross-walls consisting of submerged notches and orifices.

Figure 3. a) Initial setup showing all sensors and antennas installed upstream. b) Final setup, adapted to assess the performance of the entire fishway.

2.4. Poncebos

The studied fishway is situated on the Cares River in Asturias, on the northern coast of Spain, a tributary of the Deva River that drains into the Cantabrian Sea ($43^{\circ} 15' 52.1275''$ N, $4^{\circ} 49' 55.4316''$ W). The Cares River encompasses a basin area of 489 km^2 and maintains an average annual discharge of $10.8 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The fishway, established in the late 1950s, is part of a run-of-the-river hydropower plant (HPP) featuring a 14.4 m high dam (from the foundation) and a diversion channel approximately 5 km in length. The HPP operates with a gross head of 74 m , a maximum turbined flow of $14 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, and an installed capacity of 9.6 MW .

The fishway is of the step-pool type, comprising 20 pools linked by broad-crested notches that exhibit plunging performance. The notch geometry is atypical, featuring a substantial wall thickness of 1.6 m , a semi-circular cross-section with a variable width ($0.9 - 0.6 \text{ m}$, along the flow direction), and a longitudinal section following an Ogee or Creager profile (Figure 4). The pools average 1.85 m in length and 2.7 m in width, with depth variations along the fishway; depths are approximately 1 m in the downstream pools and can reach up to 5 m in the upstream section.

Figure 4. Geometry of Poncebos fishway.

The Smart Fishway network was implemented during the structure's second biological monitoring campaign to correlate biological passage data with the hydraulic performance of the fishway. This fishway is situated at the headwaters of the river, which promotes significant hydrological variability.

To assess the performance of the fishway, a compact Smart Fishway sensor network was installed, comprising one ultrasound node and another node equipped with ultrasound, water temperature, barometric pressure, air temperature, humidity, and luminosity sensors. This data, along with information from a PIT-Tag system with 4 antennas, was collected, processed, and transmitted (via LoRa radio + mobile connectivity) by a single Gateway using a Raspberry Pi computer.

2.5. La Nazas

Located near the village of Bera de Bidasoa in northern Spain, this fishway is situated on the Bidasoa River ($43^{\circ}17'2.4''N$ $1^{\circ}42'47.3''W$) (Figure 5a). The structure comprises nine cross-walls with submerged notches and bottom orifices (notch width (b_n) = 0.3 m; sill height (p) = 0.9 m; orifice size = 0.3 m (width- b_o) x 0.3 m (height- a_o)), and eight pools (length = 3.1 m; width = 1.6 m; slope = 10%). It features water drops (ΔH) between 0.3 – 0.4 m, a mean water depth in the pools (h_0) of 1.4 m, and a volumetric power dissipation ranging from 210 to 307 W/m³.

Figure 5. a) Smart Fishway installation at las Nazas Fishway. b) Smart Fishway installation at Bera Fishway

The sensor network for monitoring this fishway consisted of two sensors placed upstream and downstream the fishway:

- 1 node equipped with ultrasound sensors.
- 1 node equipped with ultrasound and water temperature sensors.

Furthermore, to gather biological data, a PIT-Tag system equipped with three antennas was installed. All the collected data is processed and transmitted (through LoRa radio and mobile connectivity) by a single Gateway that incorporates a Raspberry Pi computer.

In addition, a specialized PIT-Tag tracker was implemented. This device, essentially a dummy PIT-Tag, can be set to activate at regular intervals. This feature allows for the automated evaluation of the PIT-Tag System's performance, ensuring its reliability and accuracy in data collection.

2.6. Bera

The fishway is situated on the Bidasoa River, near the village of Bera de Bidasoa in northern Spain ($43^{\circ}16'13.2''N$ $1^{\circ}41'14.7''W$) (Figure 5b). Constructed with seven cross-walls featuring a free-flow pool-weir design (notch width (b_n) = 0.9 – 1.1 m; sill height (p) = 0.1 – 0.2 m), the fishway includes six pools (length = 2.5 m; width = 2 m; slope = 15%). It exhibits water drops (ΔH) ranging from 0.3 – 0.6 m, an average water depth in the pools (h_0) of 0.7 m, and a volumetric power dissipation between 120 and 235 W/m^3 . The structure of this fishway type culminates at a height of approximately 3 m, with the remaining drop created by the dam being overcome by a fish lift, which is also utilized as a monitoring station.

The sensor network for monitoring this fishway consisted of two sensors placed upstream and downstream the fishway:

- 1 node equipped with ultrasound sensors.
- 1 node equipped with ultrasound and water temperature sensors.

Furthermore, to gather biological data, a PIT-Tag system equipped with three antennas was installed. All the collected data is processed and transmitted (through LoRa radio and mobile connectivity) by a single Gateway that incorporates a Raspberry Pi computer.

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3. Gauging Stations

Gauging stations are crucial for measuring and recording water levels in rivers or canals, correlating these levels to stream discharge. While these stations serve an important societal function in river monitoring, they can negatively impact upstream fish passage by acting as potential barriers, contingent on the rivers' boundary conditions. The ability of fish to ascend through gauging weirs is influenced by their swimming and leaping capabilities, as well as the prevailing flow conditions. Certain discharge rates can lead to excessive velocities and shallow depths over the weir's downstream face, creating hydraulic barriers that hinder fish passage. Consequently, these structures exemplify how hydrological variability affects fish passage, making their study particularly pertinent for evaluating the effectiveness of Smart Fishway technology.

3.1. Agauntza

The Agauntza gauging station is located on the Agauntza River (43° 0' 57.8357" N, 2° 10' 39.0603" W), a part of the Oria River basin. The Agauntza River is one of the primary right-bank tributaries of the Oria River. The Agauntza gauging station is specifically designed for monitoring hydrological parameters, primarily streamflow. It features a small weir within the river channel, topped with a V-shaped crest (known as a V-flat) (Figure 6a). This design induces a critical spill that is simple to measure for low, medium, and high flow rates.

Despite the remote monitoring of these structures, they primarily characterize upstream water levels, enabling real-time discharge estimations. However, to assess the impact of hydrological variability on fish passage effectively, it is essential to understand the evolution of water drops in relation to discharge, necessitating the monitoring of downstream water levels. To address this, a compact sensor network was deployed, consisting of two nodes equipped with ultrasound sensors. All data was collected, processed, and transmitted (via LoRa radio + mobile connectivity) by a single gateway, consisting in a Raspberry Pi computer.

The performance of these structures in aiding fish passage has been previously assessed by the public administration, *Diputación Foral de Gipuzkoa*, with data accessible online through the use of PIT-tag systems. Previously collected biological data can be analyzed and correlated with hydraulic variables, providing insights into the impact of hydrological variability on fish passage.

3.2. Leitzaran

The Leitzaran gauging station is situated on the Leitzaran River, the most significant tributary of the Oria basin, stretching 44 km (43° 12' 32.5621" N, 2° 0' 56.0488" W). Of this, 31 km are within the province of Gipuzkoa, and the remaining 13 km are in the Foral Community of Navarra. The Leitzaran gauging station is engineered for the monitoring of hydrological parameters (streamflow, physicochemical parameters) (Figure 6b). It includes a small weir within the riverbed, topped with a V-shaped crest (known as a V-flat). This design induces a critical spill that is simple to measure for low, medium, and high flow rates.

Despite the remote monitoring of these structures, they primarily characterize upstream water levels, enabling real-time discharge estimations. However, to assess the impact of hydrological variability on fish passage effectively, it is essential to understand the evolution of water drops in relation to discharge, necessitating the monitoring of downstream water levels. To address this, a compact sensor network was deployed, consisting of two nodes equipped with ultrasound sensors. All data was collected, processed, and transmitted (via LoRa radio + mobile connectivity) by a single gateway, consisting in a Raspberry Pi computer.

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Figure 6. a) Agaunta gauging station. b) Leitzaran gauging station.

4. Hydropeaking (Portugal)

4.1. Covas do Barroso

The Covas do Barroso HPP is a run-of-river power plant, specifically designed for hydropower production. This facility, boasting an installed capacity of 6.4 MW, is engineered for a maximum discharge of 5.7 m³/s and a maximum gross head of approximately 135 m. The average annual energy production stands at 18.4 GWh.

The scheme features two intake structures, which lack flow-regulating functions, situated on the Covas River and one of its right bank tributaries, the Couto River. These intake structures comprise two concrete weirs, measuring 9.5 m and 15 m in height, respectively, Creager-type spillways, Tyrolean-type water intakes, and hydromechanical equipment.

The study site is located downstream of the powerhouse. The powerhouse itself is situated at the confluence of the Couto and Covas Rivers and encompasses a horizontal area of approximately 220 m². The Covas do Barroso HPP is positioned in northern Portugal, within the Boticas Municipality (41° 38' 31.56'' N, 7° 48' 43.46'' W). For more details, visit:

<https://ecopeak4fish.com/casestudies/#CovasdobarrosoHPP>.

The sensor setup installed at this site consisted of one node with ultrasound, water temperature, barometric pressure, air temperature, humidity, and luminosity sensors, along with an additional node with an ultrasound sensor (Figure 7b). Additionally, due to the expectation of extreme climatic events, two [MC Pressure Logger](#) were installed as a contingency plan. The data was collected and transmitted online (using LoRa radio + mobile connectivity) by a single ESP32 microcontroller. Biological information was collected using an underwater camera system, the [HydroCam](#).

4.2. Bragado

The Bragado Hydropower Plant (HPP) is situated in northern Portugal, on the Avelames River, a tributary of the Tâmega River in the Douro River basin.

The Avelames River is characterized by strong seasonal variations in flow, with the highest discharge peaks occurring during the wet semester (October-March). It also experiences significant inter-annual variations in precipitation and, consequently, in runoff, typical of rivers with a Mediterranean flow

regime. The mean long-term annual discharge at the Bragado weir is 1.4 m³/s, and the catchment area of the Avelames River at the Bragado weir section is 78.8 km². Notably, there are no other HPPs on the same river.

The water body at the Bragado HPP is classified as a natural water body with Good Ecological Status. The study site is located downstream The Bragado HPP. The Bragado HPP is located in the Vila Pouca de Aguiar Municipality in North Portugal (41° 34' 53.27" N, 7° 40' 50.95" W). More information can be found at:

<https://ecopeak4fish.com/casestudies/#BragadoHPP>.

The sensor setup installed at this site consisted of one node with ultrasound, water temperature, barometric pressure, air temperature, humidity, and luminosity sensors, along with an additional node with an ultrasound sensor (Figure 7a). Additionally, due to the expectation of extreme climatic events, two [MC Pressure Logger](#) were installed as a contingency plan. The data was collected and transmitted online (using LoRa radio + mobile connectivity) by a single ESP32 microcontroller. Biological information was collected using an underwater camera system, the [HydroCam](#).

Figure 7. a) Installation at Bragado. b) Installation at Covas do Barroso.